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THE CONCEPT AND THE IDENTITY OF THE INDIANS AS PRESENTED IN SALMAN RUSHDIE'S *THE MOOR'S LAST SIGH*

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Introduction

Rushdie is best known as the author of *The Satanic Verses* (1988), the book condemned by many Muslims as an insult to their religion. Former Iranian leader Ayatollah Khomeini called for the execution of Rushdie and his publisher, forcing the author into hiding from bounty hunters for almost a decade until the publication of *The Moor's Last Sigh* (1995). With this latest work, Rushdie chose to return to limited public exposure, and some critics have found evidence in the book to suggest that Rushdie has reconciled himself to life under threat of death. Salman Rushdie (1947-) was born in Bombay to Muslim parents, but sent to England in 1961 for his education. He has taken a degree in History from Cambridge University and has written *Grimus* (1975), *Midnight's Children* (1981), *Shame* (1983), *The Satanic Verses* (1989) and *The Last Moor's Last Sigh* (1995). The novels of Salman Rushdie deal with the representation of India (even though his boyhood was spent in Pakistan to where his family migrated after the partition) as seen by an exile. Actually Rushdie's novels, deeply immersed in rootlessness, try to recreate the past and analyze the uncertainty of the migrant. Magic realism, transculturation and hybridity emphasize the historical importance of Hindu mythology and the pluralistic nature of Indian society.

Post-colonial studies have been with us for the last forty years and at present they are foremost in any program of Literature in English. Perhaps the most interesting thing is that the current literature in English is heavily relying on the literature coming from post-colonial *topis* and post-colonial writers living in British ex-colonies or living in Britain or the United States but were born and bred in

colonized countries. The paper will not touch on British authors and novels with postcolonial themes, such as Marina Warner's *Indigo* and Zadie Smith's *White Teeth*. Its aim is to give a bird's eye view of the contemporary novel in English published from 1990-2003 and written by post colonials. Needless to say, it will neither comprise all the novels published nor most of them. Only a few, which in the author's judgment have made great repercussions in the literary world, were selected. The paper is not intended to be an in depth analysis of the novels themselves, of postcolonial themes or of the reaction of Third World literature in English against metropolitan fiction writing. The paper tries to give a summary of some novels written by the best post-colonial writers, pinpointing the themes represented, with special reference to the diaspora and transculturation.

The Moor's Last Sigh (Muhammad XI, the last Sultan of Andalusia, gave the last *sigh* in 1492 when he ended the 700-year-old Islamic domination of Spain) deals with modern India. Hailing from Bombay, the narrator, Moraes Zogoi by, nicknamed the Moor because of his descent from Muhammad, travels from the east to Spain in 1992 to discover Andalusia. Moraes is descendant from the da Gama family and specifically from Francisco da Gama, a spice exporter in Cochin (Kerala). The colonial and religious minded Epifania, Francisco's wife, utters a curse that will blight the life of the future Moraes.

Francisco and Epifania's son, Camoens, following the teachings of Nehru, would like a united India "above religion because secular, above class because socialist, above caste because enlightened" (Rushdie, 1996, p. 51). Before his death in 1939 he has a vision of the future of India: the country will immerse in violence and ethnical conflicts. Aurora, Camoens's daughter, unofficially marries Abraham Zogoi by, a Jewish clerk and villain, and Moraes, their son, is raised "neither as a Catholic nor as a Jew [...] a jew holic-anonymous" (Rushdie, 1996, p. 104). When Abraham leaves Cochin and settles in Bombay he adventures on extremely lucrative activities, such as supplying girls to the city's brothels, smuggling heroin, speculating in property, trafficking in arms and eventually in nuclear weapons.

On the other hand, Aurora is a painter who sees her children through her art. She tries to paint a fantasy *topos* called Mooristan, a place where "worlds collide, flow in and out of one another, and wash of away [...] One universe, one dimension, one country, one dream, bumpo'ing into another, or being under, or on top of. Call it Palimpsestine" (Rushdie, 1996, p. 408). Or rather, old Andalusia is painted over modern India: the present reality is overlaid with the picture of a mythic hybrid nation. India is depicted as a fatal Promised Land. Aurora's painting turns out to be a prophecy for India, or rather, "her larger, prophetic, even Cassandran fears for the nation". The painting called *The Moor's Last Sighs* shows Moraes "lost in limbo like a wandering shade: a portrait of a soul in Hell".

Cursed by his grandmothers, Moraes has a clublike right hand and he ages twice as fast as other human beings. His sexual initiation is received from a governess and he has the gift of story-telling. However, he falls under the spell of the evil mistress Uma Sarasvati, who develops a rivalry against Aurora. Moraes is expelled from home and lands in jail accused of poisoning Uma. When he is released from prison Moraes joins the Bombay underworld in the pay of Raman Fielding, a Hindu paramilitary leader. Camoens, Moraes's grandfather, had foreseen that the Hindu population, living in the villages, will be a menace to town dwellers, especially ethnic minorities. "In the city we are for secular India but the

village is for Ram... In the end I am afraid the villagers will march on the cities and people like us will have to lock our doors and there will come a Battering Ram". Such prophecy was fulfilled in Moraes's lifetime when the Babri mosque was battered down by Hindus. It is Aurora the only person who has the strength to confront the dark forces at work in India but dies when she dances during the elephant-headed god Ganesha procession and a show of Hindu-fundamentalist triumphalism.

In the meantime Fielding, closely linked to the Bombay underworld, leads the Hindu movement "against unions [...] against working women, in favour of sati, against poverty and in favour of wealth [...] against 'immigrants' to the city [...] against the corruption of the Congress [Party] and for 'direct action', by which he meant paramilitary activity in support of his political aims". He aims at a theocracy in which "one particular variant of Hinduism would rule". The rivalry between Abraham's and Fielding's underworlds comes to a head and Fielding is murdered. Although Moraes goes to Andalusia (to identify himself with Muhammad XI, or Abu-Abd-Allah, or Boabdil, in the Spanish corruption of his name) to escape the barbarism that ensues, he encounters another evil in the person of Vasco Miranda, a painter from Goa and a rival to Aurora. Miranda has stolen Aurora's Moor painting and Moraes reclaims them for his mother. Miranda imprisons him in his house until he writes his story.

In prison he meets the Japanese picture restorer Aoi Uë (a belated character in the story) who is murdered and Moraes escapes. Moraes ends his story since he is at present psychologically 72 years old, ready to die, although physically he is 36 years old. In the last chapters Moraes palimpsests himself, rather unconvincingly, as Dante, Luther and Jesus. The Alhambra in Granada is a "monument to a lost possibility [...] a testament [...] to that most profound of our needs [...] for putting an end to frontiers, for the dropping of boundaries of the self". The kind of hybridity and transculturation that Rushdie is representing is extremely provocative. Similar to the Portuguese conquest of India, the 700-year Arab domination on the Iberian Peninsula produced a healthy hybridity of culture, language and people. Moreover, the Hindu and Moslem intolerance in India is as dramatically lethal as the Christian intolerance in Spain, culminating in the Inquisition, forced baptism and the final expulsion of Moslems in 1492. Granada, sighed for by the last Muslim king Boabdil, and Bombay, sighed by Moraes, are the two cities that would have produced healthy hybridity and transculturation if intolerance had not prevailed. In fact, Moraes, attaching himself to his mother, slips to his "mother India who loved and betrayed and ate and destroyed and again loved her children, and with whom the children's passionate conjoining and eternal quarrel stretched long beyond the grave".

The essential similarity of all men and all peoples is the rational basis for transculturation. Man, he writes, should be "like an anatomy illustration from *Encyclopaedia Britannica* [...] set free from the otherwise inescapable jails of colour, race and clan", without bias and intolerance, and in all sincerity. And Rushdie verbally portrays the past and the future of India ("the great swarm of being itself") chiefly through the dark paintings of Aurora: Moraes as the Muslim Boabdil in Spain and the mythology and history of India. The novel's architecture is structured by a dynastic prelude in Cochin, Moraes's life in Bombay and the palimpsesting in Spain. The middle section is filled with "episodes" with certain characters (for example, the young businessman Adam) being introduced without any introduction and without any deep-woven roles, and slipping away just as fast. This is perhaps due to an intermingling of

the Western novel (or anti-novel) and the Hindu Panchatantra, contained self-contained narratives. *The Moor's Last Sigh* actually manifests hybridity and multiculturalism that are textually inherent to the story proposed, in which one literary tradition renews the other.

Although certain post-modern traits may be found in the novel, the problem of Moraes's "authenticity", within the context of deconstruction, sounds false. In prison Moraes asks himself whether he is on the wrong page of his own book; consequently, on a textual plane he can be insincere when he says that he is trapped within "colour, caste, sect" and longs for an authentic life outside them. Further, the importance he gives to history (the history of the Moors in Spain and especially the story of Boabdil, and the history of the Jewish community in India) deletes the post-modern stance.

Conclusion

In *The Moor's Last Sigh* Rushdie (autobiographically, perhaps) wants to show the problem of identity in the modern world. The notion of Indianness and the identity of the Indian are highly contested. The author himself is an Indian of Muslim origin who lives in Europe and the United States (especially after Khomeini's *fatwa*) and who writes about India. Whereas in *Midnight's Children*, the hero cries "Why, alone of all the more-than-five-hundred million, should I have to bear the burden of history?", Moraes says "I [want] to be Clark Kent, not any kind of Superman", with its corollary "I find that I'm a Jew". This implies notions of identity, solidarity with excluded minorities and interracial relationship.

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